

PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CHILD DEVELOPMENT ACCORDING TO MARIA MONTESSORI'S INTERPRETATION (BASED ON HER DIARIES)

TerDU Pre-school education
teacher of the department

Bobokulova Nazokat Yusufovna

Phone: +998 93 764 51 11

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10702569>

Annotation. This article describes the life and research, experiences and conclusions of Dr. Maria Montessori from Italy, Montessori collected her daily memories in a pamphlet called "Overcoming" and we used this pamphlet.

Key words: baby, child, "Overcome", sensitive period, sensitive, help, emotional development

Аннотация. В этой статье описываются жизнь и исследования, опыт и выводы доктора Марии Монтессори из Италии. Монтессори собрала свои ежедневные воспоминания в брошюре под названием «Преодоление», и мы использовали эту брошюру.

Ключевые слова: младенец, ребенок, «Преодоление», сензитивный период, сенситив, помощь, эмоциональное развитие.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Italiyalik doktor Mariya Montessorining hayoti va ilmiy tadqiqod yo'lida olib borgan izlanishlari, tajribalari va xulosalari haqida bayon etilgan, Montessori o'zining kundalik xotiralarini "Yengish" deb nomlangan risolasida jamlagan va biz ana shu risoladan foydalandik.

Kalit so'zlar: chaqaloq, bola, "Yengish", nozik davr, sezgir, yordam berish, hissiy rivojlanish

Enter.

A sense of order. One of the most important and mysterious sensitive periods is when the child is inclined to order. Its manifestation is noticeable in the first year of the baby's life and continues in the second year. Perhaps it seems strange, but

during this period, the child reacts to the external order, which is contrary to the general opinion that it is corrupt by nature.

If he lives in the closed space of a city apartment full of large and small things, it is difficult to recognize this subtle ability of a child in time. An adult child constantly removes and rearranges them for reasons incomprehensible to the child. At this time, sensitivity to its order develops, but it is met with resistance, and this causes discomfort in the child's heart. Is it because the baby starts crying for no reason and doesn't want to calm down? How do adults know the deep secrets of the soul of a small creature living next to them!

The main part. Young children show a characteristic love of order. From one and a half to two years old, they already express the need for order in their environment in clear, sometimes confusing ways. A child cannot live with a disease that experiences severe pain, and this pain can evoke a real illness in a depressed moan, in a state of prolonged excitement. A child immediately notices a disease that an adult can easily see. It is clear that the child is prone to order, which will disappear over time. Over time, sensitivity to the characteristics of the development of thinking presence is limited. We are talking about one of the most important and complete mysteries of the sensitive period.

If the environment is not suitable for the child during this period and he lives among adults, they can see very interesting signs of this sensitivity, which are not characterized by peaceful development, but by the appearance of fear, incomprehensible behavior and moodiness.

The adult child wants to make sure that the child shows positive affectivity—satisfying the child's need for order and expressing enthusiasm and joy. For this, he needs to know the psychology of children, which is already necessary in the first months of sensitive order. Our trusted babysitters tell us about examples. Thus, one nanny was surprised to see a five-month-old baby slowly sitting in a stroller, showing interest and joy at the sight of a white marble slab on a yellow wall.

Although the garden was full of beautiful flowers, the boy showed a joyful excitement as he walked across the marble slab. The kindergarten stopped in front of this stove every day, and no one thought that it could interest a five-month-old child. The joy of the child is clearly visible when this item is found in a regular place. The impact of this sensitive period can be determined by the child's reaction to the disruption of the well-known familiar order.

Another small family scene with a six-month-old baby as the main character. Once, a woman appeared in the children's room and placed her umbrella on the table. The boy was worried, but not because of the lady, but because of the umbrella, he looked at her for a while and then cried. The lady took it as the boy's wish for an umbrella and quickly handed it to the boy, smiling and saying kind words. But the boy pushed the umbrella away and continued to scream. What to do? Obviously, the mood has changed, which can be understood if you take care of the baby almost immediately after birth. The mother, who had very little knowledge of children's character, took an umbrella from the table and took it to another room. The boy immediately calmed down. The reason for his excitement was usually an extra item on an empty table. The order used to the child is broken.

The example below is with a one and a half year old baby. I myself took an active part in this scene. I was in Naples with a small group of people at the Grotto of Nero. -"Among us there was a young woman who was unable to walk as a child and who was able to carry her hand. After a while, the boy was naturally tired. That's why the mother hugged him. But he himself could not calculate its strength. He stopped taking off his coat and throwing it into his hands, getting hot. When he tried to take the child away again, he began to cry, and finally his crying turned into a scream. His mother tried in vain to calm him down. He was tired and nervous. The noise of the child got on everyone's nerves, so the whole company wanted to help the mother. The boy was walking hand in hand, but he was getting more and more worried. Everyone tried to talk to him, it was impossible and the situation got worse.

The mother had no choice but to choose another path. But after that, the nonsense went so far that the situation seemed hopeless. Here the guide intervened and with characteristic masculine energy took the boy into his strong arms. I thought there was a psychological reason behind the child's reaction. It was related to the sensitivity of the child, and I decided to make a last attempt", - I went to my mother and said: "Let me help you!" I said. He looked at me surprised, but he listened to the advice. The child immediately calmed down and began to cry, and now: "It's palda", which means: - "Yes, mother has to wear a coat on her shoulders." He seemed to think, "Finally, they understand me!"¹ He raised his hands to his mother and smiled at her, and the rest of our journey was peaceful. According to the boy, the coat should be on his shoulders and not be hung with a useless cloth in his hand. The mother's violation of such an order caused a painful conflict in the child's heart.

Other scenes I witnessed were less impressive. The mother of a two-year-old girl was sick and was lying on a chair with two pillows. The baby came and demanded a "story". What mother would you want to ask twice when her child asks for fairy tales? And he began to say, even though he felt bad, and the baby listened very attentively. But his mother felt bad and could not continue. He asked to be moved to another room and put on a bed. But the girl returned to the chair and began to cry. His mother seemed to be crying because she was sick and tried to calm him down. When the servant entered the house, he took the pillows from the chair and was about to take them to the bedroom, the little girl began to scream:

- "No, leave the pillows!" - said, as if saying: - "At least put something in its place!" - the mother's bed, despite the pain, the child He continued to tell the story, wanting to satisfy his awakened curiosity. But crying, his face filled with tears, the boy said: "Hey, chair!" he said. So his mother had to sit on a chair. The fairy tale no longer interested the boy. The mother changed the pillow and the chair, and she began to

¹ Montessori Maria "Children - others. Adults - as accused. First part"

tell a story and continued elsewhere, resulting in a dramatic, long silence in the child's heart.²

These examples show the desire to order. What is especially surprising is its early manifestation, because the need for order in two-year-old children is already the basis for practical actions, and if you interfere, it affects the spiritual life. In our children's homes, you can observe very interesting events. If the object is not in the usual place, then the two-year-old child notices this and immediately returns the object to its place. He notices everything down to the smallest detail. Adults and older children did not notice the soap lying in the sink, not in the soap dish, and passed by. If the chairs are slightly bent, then the two-year-old baby installed them correctly.

"Such cases were observed in the glass pavilion of our school during the exhibition held in San Lorenzo in the year when the Panama Canal was opened. A two-year-old boy voluntarily placed chairs on the wall after finishing his day's work at school. In this lesson, he seemed to be thinking about something. Once he put the big chair in place, he suddenly hesitated, turned again and put the chair at an angle. That's how this chair was supposed to stand."³

I want to say that the order encourages the child, calls to action. This means that it is an undoubted need for life, satisfaction brings joy. In our school, we can once again see how three- to four-year-old children willingly and happily put away the things they used after each exercise.

Order is a search for things in the room, remembering the location of each item. This means exploring the direction around you and looking at the smallest details. You can relax in a familiar environment where you can try any item with your eyes closed. Thus, exploring his surroundings, the child will be calm and happy.

² Montessori Maria "Children - others. Adults - as accused. First part"

³ www.klex.ru>nrs-Mariya Montessori,,Deti-drugie.Chast1-3''

Thus, it is clear that the love of order in children is beyond the cold and dry concept with which adults accept it.

For them, the order seems like a convenience, but it leaves them indifferent to a greater or lesser extent. But the child shapes himself with the help of the environment. Such an internal construction cannot occur according to a vague formula, but requires more precise and clear guidance.

The ground we are standing on is an order for a child. This is water for swimming fish. In early childhood, the human spirit borrows elements from the environment to provide the orientation necessary for subsequent conquests.

Young children are happy to find things in their designated places. In such games, joy is manifested, which is surprising due to the lack of a logical perspective. Before I give an example of such a game, I would like to talk about one incident that happened to Professor Piaget and his son in Geneva. -"Father first hid the object under the chair. Then, in the absence of the child, he hid it under the cushion of the second, opposite chair. The child had to find the place where he last saw the object. He could not find him there. To make the task easier, the professor hid the item in front of the boy under the cushion of the second chair. The boy raised the cushion of the first chair and stopped the search, saying: "He's not here!". The professor, who passed one subject to another in front of the child, repeated his experience. But this time the boy repeated his actions and words: "He doesn't exist!" Exasperated with the boy, the professor impatiently picked up the pillow from the second chair and asked, "Didn't you see I put it here?" "Yes," protested the boy. "- but it should be here (under the cushion of the first chair)."⁴

I myself was very surprised to see a game called "hide and seek" with two and two and a half year olds. The children seemed excited, happy and full of hope. The hide-and-seek games were as follows:-"one boy was sitting under a table that was

⁴ Children are different. Part 1-3.doc

wrapped in a table. The other children ran out of the room, but soon returned, cleared the table and "found" to the cheerful sounds of the "partner" who had been hiding during the game. This has been repeated many times. Everyone in turn said: "Now I will hide" and sat under the table. Another time, I saw the older children playing hide and seek with the younger ones. The baby hid behind the wardrobe and the adults pretended not to see him to please him. The boy shouted, "I'm here!" It was as if he said, "Didn't you see I was here?"⁵

Once I myself participated in such a game. I met a group of children at the door who were shouting and clapping their hands with joy because they had found their friend. They came to me and said: "Play with us!" Hidden! "I agreed, and everyone ran out of the room to hide. But I didn't hide behind the door, but behind the closet. When the children entered the room, they began to look for me through the door. I waited a little, and when I realized that they were not looking anymore, I left my hiding place. Children disappointed and upset. "Why don't you play with us? - they asked. "Why didn't you hide?" The game serves to awaken joy and children love this silly game very much. It was happily explained that children of a certain age should have everything. They saw the essence of the game of hide and seek and sought to find something that could not be seen, but they knew exactly where it was. They clearly say: "Although it is not visible, I know where it can be, and even close my eyes, because I am sure where it is hidden."

All this indicates that nature has increased sensitivity in the child to form an inner consciousness, which does not distinguish between things because it recognizes the connection between things. This feeling turns the whole environment of the child into a whole, the parts of which are in certain relationships. In such an environment where he is familiar with relationships, the child wants to learn how to act and achieve goals. Without the ability to make a connection, he has no real foundation, and he feels like a person who has furniture but no apartment to put it

⁵ <https://iknigi.net>avtor-mariya-montess>

in. Why does the child have a large number of pictures that make an impression in an order that cannot be meaningfully integrated? If a person knows the things around him, but does not know the connection between them, then he will not find a way out of this chaos. At the same time, the child carries out preparatory work, on the basis of which adults can travel through life and find their own way. In sensitive periods of influence, nature teaches a person as before. He is like a teacher who forces a student to draw a plan of a schoolroom and use it to prepare a map of the hemispheres representing the entire surface of the earth. We can also say that during this period, nature gives the child a compass in his hand, with which he can navigate the sea.

In addition, another gift from nature is the ability to accurately reproduce the sounds that give rise to speech with their endlessly developing abilities, which baby adults have been reproducing for centuries. The human mind does not appear from scratch. A child is built on a foundation that rests in his tender years.

Internal order. In the child, sensitivity to order exists in two forms: both a sense of external order in relation to the connections between the components of the world, and a sense of internal order, which can be called a sense of internal orientation. It consists in the recognition and localization of physical functions that interact with each other during movement.

The inner sense of direction has been studied by experimental psychology. At the same time, the "feeling of the muscles" has manifested itself, which allows us to constantly report on the various positions of the organs of our body. Holding hands with him is a special memory called a special muscle. Mechanistic theories based on experiences of conscious movements were conducted along this path. If a person makes a movement with his hand to pick up something, then this movement is felt by the muscle sensation, it is stored in the muscle memory and can be repeated at any time. Thus, a person forms a sense of internal orientation, which makes a voluntary movement, for example, turning in different directions with the right or

left hand. All this is done on the basis of the experience accumulated during the performance of the individual actions mentioned by him rationally and willingly.

Some facts contradict each other with this explanation. A child has a very bright sensitive period for the development of the body. Before the child begins to move freely and thus accumulate his experience, he announces himself. This means that nature prepares a special sensitivity for the development of the body to occupy different positions.

The old theories refer to the purely mechanical connections of the nervous system. We are talking about subtle periods related to spiritual processes, enlightenment and vibrations that make up consciousness. These are the energies that arise from the zero state to ensure the existence of the basic connections that will carry out the spiritual construction of the future. Nature gives a start to everything as a gift to the child, thanks to which the conscious experience is improved. Negative effects on delicate periods and their duration are carried out when the child encounters obstacles around him. Then there is often a strong excitement, which gives us certain mood symptoms. A child may even wake up with an incurable disease when the conditions that cause it arise. It is only necessary to remove the barrier, and immediately the "nonsense" and the disease will disappear. Facts described by a nanny from England, who had to leave the child for some time under the supervision of another experienced nanny. He had no difficulty with the baby until he came to the bath, which was uncomfortable and the child's desperate cries. Not only did he scream, but he defended himself by using his arms and legs to push the nanny away, and his efforts were futile. In the end, the child hated the mother. When the first babysitter came back, she was sweet and friendly again. Without the child's resistance, he could bathe the baby. On the contrary, he was happy with this bath. The first nanny was from our school. He thought about these circumstances to explain the child's behavior. He patiently searched for reasons for what was happening.

When both nannies discussed the situation, they discovered that one of them was holding the child in his right hand with his head and legs on his left side, while the other was used to holding him differently. Thus, he found that the baby saw "evil" in his colleague, because he held it "oppositely".

In another case that I would like to tell you about, the child came into a state of intense excitement, which took on a painful form. The reason for this was determined with great difficulty. I did not work as a doctor at that time, but I had to participate in the resolution of the conflict. This child was six months old. The family returned from a long trip, which, according to the recollections, was due to the child's excessive stress. According to the parents, there were no accidents during the trip. The family lived in first-class hotels, in pre-ordered rooms, with a crib prepared for the child for this ceremony and meals.

On the next trip, the family stayed in a comfortably furnished apartment. But there was no crib in it, and the boy slept on a big bed next to his mother. The baby's illness began at night in a very serious condition. He had to be carried in his arms at night, and his cries were associated with abdominal pain. Several doctors were invited, one of whom even advised the child to prepare food carefully. But neither baths nor modern methods of treatment had the slightest effect. The child's condition continued to deteriorate, and each subsequent night became more difficult for the family. Convulsions were added to this. The boy was lying on a bed of horrors. Such seizures occurred two to three times a day. It was decided to consult a well-known specialist in children's neurology. That's when I intervened. The child seemed healthy, and according to the parents' account, he was healthy and calm throughout the trip. Thus, -“the signs indicated the causes of the spiritual order. Realizing this, I put the child to bed and again saw the state of awakening. I took two chairs and put them on top of each other so that they became a plush bed. Then he covered the bed with a sheet and without another word placed it next to the big bed. The child looked,

began to cry, and lay down on the edge of the big bed, then on the useless bed, and immediately fell asleep. The symptoms of the disease no longer appeared."⁶

Obviously, the child was used to sleeping in a small cradle, which covered him from all sides and served as a support for his body. A large bed could not provide him with such protection, and this disorder in his inner direction caused the full suffering of the conflict. Doctors are looking for a means to prevent futile procedures. This is the effect of sensitive periods. It is in them that the arrows of nature are directed.

A child does not behave like us. We collected a lot of impressions, and from that they became blurred. But the child does not come from nothing, and he is still very poor. And everything he creates starts from scratch. He takes this constructive effort alone and makes it his legacy. We are like the children of a man who has earned wealth by the sweat of his brow, but we do not want to understand it. We are cold and ungrateful. We like our superiority. After all, we are already provided with everything and do not need to do anything. We can use the ideas that the child has prepared for us; His will for us; the muscles he filled with strength.

We lead the world because the child brought us all the skills we need. We are aware of ourselves because this sensitivity was prepared for us by the child. Therefore we are rich, because we are the heirs of the child, and our foundation was brought to them from the void. The child does not hear the first step from this void to the path of knowledge. Thus, approaching us is the main source of our vital activity. Whatever happens, it must happen according to the plan of creation, without any fuss, without leaving memories in the human brain.

Literature analysis. When we talk about the scientific path of Maria Montessori, we emphasize that she created a method that made a radical change in the education system of the whole world. This method became the basis for the

⁶ "Karapuz" nashriyoti, 2012 yil

development of education, free education. Also: "In this regard, today the sociality of the individual is increasing and gaining importance. The student person plays an important role in the life of the society because the student is a social group that manifests itself in activities of high social significance, consciously aimed at solving the problems facing the society"⁷

In addition, the method widely promoted by Montessori has spread to all countries of the world, in particular: "In our republic, the education system is always under the attention of the state. During the past period, complex organizational and legal measures were implemented to create an effective preschool education system aimed at ensuring the formation of a healthy and comprehensively developed generation"⁸.

Summary. Based on this life experience, it can be concluded that every pedagogue, in the way of his research, definitely serves to develop education, to open new facets and secrets, and this path is considered a very difficult and honorable path. . The application of our method, which we have shown at the end of our article, gives the most effective results in education.

References:

1. Montessori Maria "Children - others. Adults - as accused. First part"
2. Montessori Maria "Children - others. Adults - as accused. First part"
3. www.klex.ru/nrs-Maria Montessori,,Deti-drugie.Chast1-3"
4. Children are different. Part 1-3.doc
5. <https://\iknigi.net.avtor-mariya-montess...>
6. K.E. Summative introduction. and conclusion. articles, reviews, 2012
7. "Karapuz" publishing house, 2012

⁷ Abjalova Hilola Rakhmat kizi Using cooperative methods in forming the social activities of students

⁸ Prатов Saidmurad Irgashovich Pedagogical mechanisms of finding feelings of tolerance in children during game activity

8. Abjalova Hilola Rakhmat kizi "Using cooperative methods in forming the social activities of students"
9. Prator Saidmurad Irgashovich "Pedagogical mechanisms of finding feelings of tolerance in children during game activity"